

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIALS

Supplemental Table 1. Inclusion criteria, exclusion criteria, and list of codes.

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria	
<p>Inclusion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adult patients who underwent one or more imaging modalities (see below) in Mayo Clinic Rochester, Jacksonville, Scottsdale or Midwest Healthcare System from 07/01/2017 to 09/30/2023. • Only the first image is included. <p>Exclusion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Previous diagnosis of thyroid cancer, thyroid nodule, partial or total thyroidectomy, thyroid biopsy or hyperthyroidism (see below). • No research authorization. • Less than 12 months of previous visits/care at Mayo Clinic. 	
Image Description	Code (CPT)
PET and PET/CT	G0210-G0234, G0252-G0254, G0330-G0336, 78608, 78810, 78811-78813, 78814-78816
CT neck	70480-70492
CT chest	71250, 71260, 71270
CT cervical spine	72125-71127
CT angiography neck	70498
CT angiography chest	71275
MRA neck or chest	70547, 70549, 70540, 70543
MRI cervical spine	72141, 72142, 72156
MRI Orbit, face, neck	70540, 70542, 70543
MRI chest	71550, 71551, 71552
Ultrasound Carotid	93880
Face, head and neck soft tissue	76536
Parathyroid scan	78070
Octreotide scan	78804, 78999
Nuclear cardiac stress test	78452, 93017
Diagnosis/Procedure Description	Code
Thyroid Cancer	ICD-9: 193 ICD-10: C73
Cystic Thyroid Nodule	ICD-9: 246.2
Thyroid Nodule	ICD-9: 226, 241.0, 241.1, 240.0, 241.9, 246.2 ICD-10: D34 E01.1 D44.0 E04.1 E04.2 HCPCS: G9552
Thyroidectomy	CPT: 60212, 60225, 60240, 60252, 60254, 60270, 60271
Partial Thyroidectomy	CPT: 60210, 60220
Thyroid nodule biopsy	CPT: 60001, 60100, 60300
Hyperthyroidism	ICD-9: 242.01, 242.10, 242.11, 242.20, 242.21, 242.30, 242.31, 242.40, 242.41, 242.80, 242.81, 242.90, 242.91, 245.0, 245.0, 245.1, 245.3, 245.4 ICD-10: E05.00, E05.10, E05.20

Supplemental Table 2. Annotation Dictionary

Category	Description	Example
Incidental finding	Header of the reports **Annotate to be able to save all the reports (with and without incidental findings)	
Normal findings	Words that describe observation of normal thyroid gland	Without category options, no relevant for analysis. Examples: normal, unremarkable
Thyroid	Presence of the word thyroid in the radiology report, to start the screening workflow. ** Words “goiter” and “thyromegaly” are going to be annotated under this category just the first time they are mentioned in the report, and just in case the word “thyroid” is not written in the report. If they appear more times, the following will be annotated as “type of finding”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Thyroid (e.g., thyroid, thyroid gland) ✓ Goiter ✓ Thyromegaly
Type of finding	The classification of the incidental finding in the thyroid gland.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Nodular (e.g., nodule, nodularity, nodular, multinodular, multinodular goiter, multinodular enlargement, goitrous enlargement, lesion, lesions, cyst, cysts, mass) ✓ Non-nodular (e.g., atrophy, atrophic, foci, focus, congenitally absent, remnant, enlargement, enlarged, calcification, calcified, ectopic tissue, thyroglossal duct, thyromegaly)
Number of findings	Number of thyroid incidental findings described either in a qualitative or quantitative form.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Single (e.g., single, one, 1, sole, unique) ✓ Multiple
Size	Size of the thyroid finding, reported either as a quantitative or qualitative characteristic (e.g., 4.6 cm, 12 mm, tiny, small, massive)	
Location	Refers to the specific location within the thyroid gland where the incidental finding is located.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Right lobe (e.g., right, right lobe, right thyroid lobe, right thyroid) ✓ Left lobe (e.g., left, left lobe, left thyroid lobe, left thyroid) ✓ Isthmus ✓ Bilateral
Radiological characteristics	Other radiological characteristics of the thyroid incidental finding, specific of the imaging modality used.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Density (e.g., hypodense, hyperdense, low dense, low density) ✓ Attenuation (e.g., hypoattenuating, hyperattenuating, heterogeneous attenuation, low attenuating) ✓ Metabolic activity (e.g., hypermetabolic, hypermetabolic, FDG activity, FDG uptake, SUV) ✓ Enhancement (e.g., hypoenhancing, hyperenhancing, normal enhancement) ✓ Calcification, calcifications, calcified

<p>Associated findings</p>	<p>Other findings in the imaging report outside the thyroid but related to the thyroid finding.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Trachea invasion (e.g., tracheal FDG uptake, tracheal mass/lesion, trachea erosion, trachea invasion, tracheal wall thickening) ✓ Trachea non-invasion (e.g., narrowing of the upper trachea, tracheal deviation) ✓ Carotid/Jugular invasion (e.g., invasion of the vessel walls, irregular margin of the wall, loss of vascular wall layers, contour irregularities) ✓ Carotid/Jugular non-invasion (e.g., carotid/jugular stenosis, lateral deviation) ✓ Esophagus invasion (e.g., esophagus FDG uptake, esophagus mass/lesion, esophagus erosion, esophagus invasion, esophagus wall thickening) ✓ Esophagus non-invasion (e.g., esophageal narrowing, esophagus deviation) ✓ Nerve invasion ✓ Nerve non-invasion (e.g., dysfunction of the recurrent pharyngeal nerve, displaced nerve) ✓ Vocal cords invasion (e.g., mass/irregularity of vocal cord, distortion of laryngeal soft tissue, increased radiotracer uptake) ✓ Vocal cords non-invasion (e.g., vocal cord not medialized, vocal cord paralysis) ✓ Cartilage invasion (e.g., erosion/destruction of thyroid/cricoid cartilage) ✓ Cartilage non-invasion ✓ Bone invasion (e.g., osteolytic/osteoblastic bone lesion, pathological fracture, focal increased uptake/metabolic activity) ✓ Bone non-invasion ✓ Muscle invasion (e.g., muscle mass/lesion, muscle thickening, focal increased uptake/metabolic activity) ✓ Muscle non-invasion ✓ Other (e.g., thyroid extend into the thoracic inlet)
<p>Radiology classification</p>	<p>Classification of the thyroid incidental finding, according to its characteristics in the image, given by the radiologist in the report.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Benign (e.g., benign, likely benign, insignificant by size criteria, insignificant) ✓ Malignant (e.g., malignant, pathological, likely malignant, likely pathological, likely cancer) ✓ Indeterminate
<p>Recommendation</p>	<p>Recommendations given by the radiologist related to the thyroid incidental finding (e.g., [image/biopsy] recommended, follow-up recommended, correlation recommended, nonemergent ultrasound recommended, consider [image/biopsy])</p>	<p>Recommendation for thyroid incidental finding (yes/no)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical input needed - Further imaging needed

Supplemental Table 3. Additional Information about applied models.

Model	Description	Pre-Training Corpus	Key Features
BERT-base	Foundational version of BERT, designed to capture deep contextual relationships within text through bidirectional training. Used as a baseline model in this study.	BooksCorpus and English Wikipedia	General-purpose training; lacks domain-specific pre-training for medical text.
RoBERTa	An optimized version of BERT with improved training parameters, such as removal of the next-sentence prediction objective and use of larger mini-batches and learning rates. Well-suited for nuanced language comprehension tasks.	Extended corpus including books and English Wikipedia	Enhanced understanding of language dynamics; lacks biomedical-specific pre-training.
Medical-NER	A specialized model fine-tuned from DeBERTa, which incorporates disentangled attention mechanisms to better understand word relationships. Specifically trained for biomedical tasks using domain-specific corpora.	PubMed dataset	Domain-specific training for medical terminology and text structure; excels in identifying clinical entities within thyroid radiology reports.

Supplemental Table 4. Comparative performance of the models in the identification of ITNs.

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
BERT-base	0.66	0.33	0.50	0.40
BioBERT	0.94	0.92	0.95	0.93
Bio_ClinicalBERT	0.97	0.96	0.98	0.97
Gatortron-base	0.81	0.82	0.86	0.81

Supplemental Table 5. Comparative performance of the models in the characterization of ITNs.

Model	Entity	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Accuracy
BERT-base	Location	0.64	0.78	0.70	0.82
	Radiological Characteristics	0.83	0.83	0.83	
	Size	0.75	0.90	0.82	
	Recommendation	0.50	0.50	0.50	
	Average	0.75	0.82	0.78	
Medical-NER	Location	0.89	0.89	0.89	0.85
	Radiological Characteristics	0.82	0.75	0.78	
	Size	0.64	0.90	0.75	
	Recommendation	1.00	1.00	1.00	
	Average	0.78	0.85	0.81	
RoBERTa-base	Location	0.70	0.64	0.67	0.60
	Radiological Characteristics	0.38	0.56	0.45	
	Size	0.35	0.70	0.47	
	Recommendation	0.50	0.33	0.40	
	Average	0.47	0.60	0.52	

Supplemental Table 6. Charlson comorbidity index - Incidental Findings vs Non-Incidental.

	Incidental Findings		Odds Ratio (95% CI) ¹
	No (N=106606)	Yes (N=9077)	
Charlson Comorbidity Count, n (%)			
0	75430 (70.8%)	6212 (68.4%)	Ref
1	20820 (19.5%)	1918 (21.1%)	1.12 (1.06, 1.18)
2	6425 (6.0%)	578 (6.4%)	1.09 (1.00, 1.19)
3+	3931 (3.7%)	369 (4.1%)	1.14 (1.02, 1.27)
Sum of Diseases: Mean (SD)	0.4 (0.86)	0.5 (0.87)	1.04 (1.02, 1.07)
Severity Weighted Sum: Mean (SD)	0.7 (1.47)	0.8 (1.59)	1.04 (1.03, 1.06)
Age weighted severity sum: Mean (SD)	2.2 (2.16)	2.6 (2.22)	1.09 (1.08, 1.10)
Comorbidities Present:			
Aids, n (%)	90 (0.1%)	4 (0.0%)	
Cerebrovascular Disease, n (%)	1317 (1.2%)	88 (1.0%)	
CHF, n (%)	2764 (2.6%)	220 (2.4%)	
CPD, n (%)	6454 (6.1%)	484 (5.3%)	
Dementia, n (%)	818 (0.8%)	62 (0.7%)	
Diabetes, n (%)	7288 (6.8%)	662 (7.3%)	
Diabetes Organ Damage, n (%)	2978 (2.8%)	264 (2.9%)	
Hemiplegia, n (%)	184 (0.2%)	7 (0.1%)	
Liver Disease, n (%)	710 (0.7%)	38 (0.4%)	
Metastatic Solid Tumor, n (%)	1273 (1.2%)	162 (1.8%)	
Mild Liver Disease, n (%)	2643 (2.5%)	191 (2.1%)	
Other Cancer, n (%)	9936 (9.3%)	1156 (12.7%)	
Peripheral Vascular Disease, n (%)	2978 (2.8%)	252 (2.8%)	
Renal Disease, n (%)	5409 (5.1%)	543 (6.0%)	
Rheumatologic Disease, n (%)	1793 (1.7%)	146 (1.6%)	
Ulcer, n (%)	313 (0.3%)	28 (0.3%)	

¹Univariate logistic regression.

Supplemental Table 7. Ordering clinician characteristics.

	Total (N=8897)	Clinicians with at least 1 Incidental
Specialty, n (%)		
Emergency Medicine	613 (7.1%)	417 (12.6%)
Pulmonary Medicine	226 (2.6%)	157 (4.7%)
Hematology Oncology	468 (5.4%)	240 (7.2%)
Medical Oncology	294 (3.4%)	160 (4.8%)
Neurology	676 (7.8%)	259 (7.8%)
Cardiovascular	666 (7.7%)	186 (5.6%)
Internal Medicine	841 (9.7%)	310 (9.3%)
Family Medicine	1074 (12.4%)	390 (11.7%)
Other	3805 (43.9%)	1201 (36.2%)
Gender, n (%)		
Female	4154 (47.9%)	1516 (45.7%)
Male	4526 (52.1%)	1804 (54.3%)
Credentials, n (%)		
Physicians	6383 (73.3%)	2528 (76.0%)
Mid-Level Practitioners	1802 (20.7%)	659 (19.8%)
Nurses	100 (1.1%)	28 (0.8%)
Advanced practice providers	234 (2.7%)	58 (1.7%)
Associate clinicians	41 (0.5%)	10 (0.3%)
Others	151 (1.7%)	42 (1.3%)
Patients¹: Mean (Std)	13.0 (24.4)	2.7 (3.2)

¹Patient count who meet criteria and are part of cohort. Mean number of patients per clinician.

Supplemental Table 8. Odds ratios for multivariable analysis.

Characteristic	Levels	Odds Ratio (95% CI)
Sex	Female	1.83 (1.75, 1.92)
	Male	Ref
Patient Age	5-year increments	1.095 (1.09, 1.10)
BMI	5-unit increments	1.03 (1.01, 1.04)
Specialty	Emergency Medicine	Ref
	Cardiovascular	1.25 (1.10, 1.43)
	Internal Medicine	1.64 (1.49, 1.81)
	Family Medicine	1.38 (1.25, 1.51)
	Medical Oncology	2.12 (1.90, 2.37)
	Hematology Oncology	2.05 (1.86, 2.27)
	Neurology	1.36 (1.23, 1.51)
	Pulmonary Medicine	1.44 (1.30, 1.59)
	Other	1.92 (1.79, 2.05)
Modality	Body Group	Ratio of Odds Ratios
CT	Chest	Ref
	Head	0.59 (0.51, 0.67)
	Neck	3.41 (3.20, 3.63)
	Mixed	1.13 (1.02, 1.24)
MRI	Chest	0.25 (0.16, 0.39)
	Head	0.12 (0.04, 0.34)
	Neck	0.27 (0.10, 0.75)
	Mixed	0.39 (0.14, 1.06)
Nuclear Medicine	Chest	3.07 (2.05, 4.58)
	Head	0.49 (0.12, 1.99)
	Neck	25.54 (9.77, 66.00)
	Mixed	0.87 (0.33, 2.21)
PET	Chest	5.90 (3.74, 9.30)
	Head	0.14 (0.04, 0.56)
	Neck	4.83 (1.32, 17.89)
	Mixed	0.73 (0.27, 1.96)
Ultrasound	Chest	0.07 (0.03, 0.18)
	Head	0.17 (0.02, 1.60)
	Neck	0.12 (0.02, 0.83)
	Mixed	0.38 (0.03, 5.73)

Supplemental Table 9. Thyroid cancer histology and sizes.

	Incidental Findings			P-value
	No (N=106606)	Yes (N=9077)	Total (N=115683)	
Histology, n (%)				0.2547 ¹
Anaplastic Thyroid Carcinoma	1 (4.8%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (0.8%)	
Follicular Thyroid Carcinoma	0 (0.0%)	2 (1.8%)	2 (1.5%)	
Hurthle Cell Carcinoma	1 (4.8%)	6 (5.5%)	7 (5.4%)	
Medullary Thyroid Carcinoma	0 (0.0%)	4 (3.7%)	4 (3.1%)	
Metastasis from external source	0 (0.0%)	1 (0.9%)	1 (0.8%)	
Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma	19 (90.5%)	96 (88.1%)	115 (88.5%)	
Missing	106585	8968	115553	
Size (mm)				0.0499 ²
Mean (SD)	12.8 (7.81)	19.7 (14.43)	18.6 (13.82)	
Missing	106586	8969	115555	

¹Chi-Square p-value; ²Kruskal-Wallis p-value.

FIGURES

Supplemental Figure 1. Annotation flowchart.

Supplemental Figure 2. An overview of the incidental nodular thyroid reports identification pipeline.

Supplemental Figure 3. An overview of the target entities recognition pipeline using incidental nodular thyroid reports.

Supplemental Figure 4. Interactions between body location and imaging modality.

MRI: Magnetic Resonance Imaging; PET: Positron Emission Tomography; CT: Computed Tomography.

